

Biological Significance of Plant Peroxidase Enzyme

Kasimova Iroda Unvanovna

Lecturer Department of Zoology and Biochemistry Andijan State University 170100, Andijan, University St. Bd. 129, Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: A number of basic biochemical processes that take place in every living organism, including respiration, nutrition, and energy exchange, take place in the presence of enzymes. An example of this is the peroxidase enzyme found in plants. This article provides information on the biological significance of plant peroxidase. Peroxidase is one of the most widely used enzyme proteins, and interest in its study has not diminished over the years. The presence of this enzyme in the tissues of plants and animals, as well as in the composition of fungi and bacteria, makes it an important combination of higher and lower organisms.

Keywords: phytopathogen, enzyme, hydrogen peroxide, fraction, spectrophotometry, isoperoxidase, gem-containing peroxidases.

INTRODUCTION

Enzymes act as biological catalysts in all living organisms. In the life of plants, enzymes are very important compounds that control a number of biochemical processes. One of the most important enzymes involved in biochemical reactions in the plant cell is the peroxidase enzyme. Determining the isozyme spectrum of this enzyme not only in plants, but also in other living organisms and its role in cellular processes in the life of a living organism allows solving a number of problems of today's agriculture and medicine. In addition, considering the use of this enzyme in today's biotechnological practical processes, it is important to solve the cleaning problems.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The first evidence of the existence of the enzyme peroxidase dates back to 1855, when Schönbein began to observe its formation as a decomposition product when he mixed a number of organic substances with plant and animal extracts and hydrogen peroxide.

The first work on the identification of peroxidase is the work entitled "Study of the role of peroxide in the chemistry of living cells" in 1902. In the course of these researches carried out together with A. N. Bach and R. Shoda in 1903, a partially purified preparation of peroxidase was obtained from horseradish roots [1].

The name "peroxidase" was given to this enzyme by Linoze, who was one of the first to describe the difference between "oxidase" and "peroxidase". To date, this enzyme has been isolated from fungi of the *Aspergillus* genus *Aspergillus niger* and a number of fungi and horseradish plants, and horseradish peroxidase is widely used in practice [2].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Peroxidases are a class of enzymes widely distributed in plants and can be easily isolated from most plant cells and organs. Peroxidase enzyme controls oxidation-reduction processes in biochemical processes in

plant cells. This enzyme belongs to the class of oxidoreductases and has a unique coenzyme and specificity [3].

Peroxidase is a two-component enzyme that contains compounds of active groups, and these groups chemically interact with the substrate, or otherwise interact with kolloid proteins with the help of these active groups to increase catalytic activity. The peroxidase enzyme is a globular protein with a diameter of 50Å and 43% α -helical parts in the protein part. Peroxidase enzyme is an enzyme that acts on hydrogen peroxide as an acceptor, adopted in 1979 international convention on enzyme nomenclature [4].

The primary structure of peroxidase was studied by Velinder et al. They found that 203 to 300 amino acid residues can enter the primary protein structure [5].

The main properties of peroxidase are catalyzing the oxidation of chemical compounds with the formation of intermediate complexes with different spectral characteristics at the expense of peroxygen. Currently, 4 types of complexes have been identified. The complex is formed immediately upon addition of H₂O₂ (hydrogen peroxide) and is usually rapidly converted to complex II, complex III and IV are compounds formed in excess of peroxide. Complexes III and IV do not have catalytic activity, their formation leads to inhibition of the reaction [6].

Picture. Primary structure of the peroxidase enzyme. The hemin part of peroxidase.

The enzyme is not only a peroxidase, but also an oxidase, in which it catalyzes the oxidation of a number of compounds at the expense of unactivated molecular oxygen. The oxidase function was first identified by Teorelyu. In some plants, he identified an enzyme that oxidizes dihydroxyfumaric acid (OGF) with the absorption of oxygen, and the enzyme is peroxidase. The oxidase function of the enzyme is manifested in the interaction with various chemical compounds. A necessary condition for the oxidase reaction is the presence of manganese cofactor ions and various phenolic compounds [7].

Hydro - naphthoquinones, indolyl acetic acid, reduced coenzymes NAD*H₂ and NADP*H₂ serve as substrates for the manifestation of the oxidase function of peroxidase. Research was also conducted to study the conditions of oxidation of NAD and NAD*H by peroxidases [8].

The role of peroxidase in the emergence of the oxygelase function characteristic of ribulose diphosphate carboxylase oxygelase in higher plants was shown. The peroxidases in the roots of Barley and Limosella showed oxygenase properties in addition to peroxidase and oxidase, but the presence of copper ions was necessary for the reaction. In some reactions, the presence of cofactors is necessary for the manifestation of peroxidase catalytic activity. Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ca²⁺ and other metals or complex organic compounds temporarily interacting with the peroxidase molecule can act as cofactors for this enzyme [9].

The above indicates that peroxidase can be a regulatory factor, exhibiting different enzymatic activity.

In addition, it is able to change the activity of its specific functional groups, which is necessary for the fetment to show its catalytic effect more fully, by means of covalent or ionic modification. Among them are the three carboxyl groups of the peroxidase active protein involved in the oxidation of O-dianisidine. There is extensive evidence that peroxidases are related to several physiological events, and peroxidases have been shown to play an active role in metabolism. An important function of peroxidases in plants is related to lignin synthesis. In addition to lignification, their potential role in development is determined by peroxidase activity in indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) catabolism and ethylene biosynthesis, both of which are plant hormones. The broad spectrum of peroxidase activity and its participation in various physiological processes correspond to its relative non-specificity for substrates and the emergence of various isozymes [10].

In recent years, one of the enzymes widely used all over the world is the peroxidase enzyme. Peroxidase is one of the most common enzyme proteins and is of increasing interest in its study. The presence of this enzyme in the tissues of plants and animals, as well as in the composition of fungi and bacteria, gives grounds for considering it as an important compound of higher and lower organisms.

According to a number of authors, this enzyme is a stress enzyme, especially in plants growing in various extreme conditions (arid and saline soils), in plants infected with various phytopathogens, the amount of this enzyme is higher than healthy o It has been shown in many literatures that it is several times higher than plants [11].

When pathological conditions occur in plants, it causes the amount of peroxidase enzyme to change, that is, to increase. It enhances the catalytic functions of the enzyme. Currently, high-sensitivity biosensors have been produced based on recombinant peroxidases, which are used for the detection of various compounds in complex multicomponent mixtures, as well as in the analysis of environmental pollution. In recent years, peroxidase preparations isolated from new sources have appeared on the market [12].

The most effective enzyme today is peroxidase with high stability under extreme conditions, which is a recombinant variant of fungal peroxidase [13].

CONCLUSION

In short, the peroxidase enzyme has a very high biological value in the plant organism. Peroxidase performs many biochemical processes, controls the oxidation-reduction process. Today, despite the fact that the price of peroxidase enzyme is somewhat expensive, we can isolate it from many plants found in nature, and study its properties, dynamics, and quantitative changes in the composition of plants infected with the virus.

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